

INTERNATIONAL PUBLIC CALL FOR LITERATURE – Year 2022

100 years of the Communist Party of Brazil -PCdoB

Year: 2022

Category: Literature (Poetry)

The Fundação Maurício Grabois (FMG) and Editorial CEALA will select 100 poems to be part of a collection to be published in DIGITAL and/or PRINT format, nationally and internationally, on the occasion of the celebrations of the 100th anniversary of the Communist Party of Brazil.

The final selection of the poems will be made no later than 60 calendar days after **15 May 2022 (date extended), the deadline for receipt** of the works.

GUIDELINES AND CRITERIA

1. The poems must deal with one or more of these themes: socialism, freedom, social justice, solidarity among people, defense of free culture expression and collective struggles;
2. Participants will have full aesthetic freedom and may submit their work in any language, as long as it is accompanied by the corresponding Portuguese translation;
3. The poems may or may not be published¹;
4. Each participant may submit up to 2 poems;
5. Poems must be in the appropriate font format (v 12 point size and Arial or Times New Roman type), with a maximum length of 2 pages;
6. The author(s) must provide the following information in a maximum of 5 lines and in 12-point Arial or Times New Roman font: full name and artistic name (if any), biographical profile, nationality, title of the poem and contact details (email(s), WhatsApp, website, etc.);
7. The Fundação Maurício Grabois and CEALA will appoint a commission of members working in the cultural and, mainly, literary areas, which will

¹ Author(s) is(are) responsible for ensuring that their rights do not prohibit or prevent the publication or dissemination of the work submitted.

select the 100 poems;

8. The works must be sent by e-mail only, to the address cealaconsulting@hotmail.com, specifying the 'subject' field "CALM PÚBLICA DE LITERATURA - 100 anos PCdoB - 2022".

9. The Fundação Maurício Grabois and Editorial CEALA will not retain the copyright of the poems sent, they will belong to the respective author(s), but with the due cession of publication rights to the institutions organizing the book object of this Public Call for Literature (CPL).

9. This CPL is not characterized as an award, nor is it for profit. The initiative will allow wide dissemination of works by selected authors.

10. If you have any question, please send an email to cealaconsulting@hotmail.com

Join ans share this invitation!

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